

Database of Negative Reviews from Patients of Medical Clinics in Russian Cities with a Population of over a Million (Based on infodoctor.ru for the Period 2012–2023)

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Abstract

This database contains 18.492 negative patient reviews (rated one star out of five, where five is the highest level of medical service quality) from the Russian medical review aggregator infodoctor.ru, collected between July 2012 and August 2023. The database is presented in .xlsx format (UTF-8 encoding). The dataset covers 16 major Russian cities, including Moscow (8.108 reviews), St. Petersburg (2.356), and 14 other cities with a population of over a million (8.028). Reflecting dissatisfaction with the quality of medical services, this dataset provides important information about the problems in the healthcare delivery across regions and socio-demographic groups. The data are presented as full-text reviews, which allows for an in-depth analysis of patient experience using text content analysis. Structured variables such as city, date, complaint type, doctor's specialty, patient's gender also allow for quantitative analysis using econometric methods. The combination of methods allows us to gain insight into patient dissatisfaction with medical services in Russian cities with a population of over a million for more than a decade.

Keywords

database, big data, patient reviews, Russia, quality of medical services, patient dissatisfaction, regional differentiation, gender differences, medical professional groups, doctors, clinics, treatment, organization of medical services

JEL codes: C45, I11, I18, J10

Data format and access

The database consists of full-text patient reviews, reflecting their dissatisfaction with health-care quality. Materials in Russian have been posted in the «Review list» of the site infodoctor.ru. Publication period: July 2012 to August 2023. The database consists of 18.492 reviews covering 16 Russian cities with population of over one million.

Data format: **.xlsx**.

Data access: **10.5281/zenodo.15257447**

Data collection methodology

Sociological studies (e.g., van de Mortel 2008) emphasize that positive reviews often reflect not the actual quality of services, but social norms (e.g., gratitude for the help provided) or fear of condemnation. Negative reviews in anonymous sources allow us to see specific shortcomings. The authors analyzed negative reviews collected from 16 Russian cities with a population of over one million, for which they managed to form representative samples (at least 1000 reviews per city). The selection of material was carried out from the guest book section of the infodoctor.ru website according to the evaluation criterion “one star out of five”, where five stars are the highest rating for the quality of service. Thus, the criterion clearly identifies the review as negative. Duplicates were excluded from the database, and personal data in the texts were replaced with the sign “#####”.

Three variables were added for each review:

1. Author's gender. The author's gender was determined based on his/her name (if available) or linguistic markers that allow identifying the author's gender in the review texts. In 91.3% of cases, gender was successfully identified. Otherwise, we put “0” – gender cannot be determined.
2. The type of complaint. The classification of complaint types is intended to facilitate the management of the regional healthcare system (this is the main element of the database's novelty). The complaint type was classified into three categories: “M-type” – medical problems (quality of diagnostics, treatment, lack of effectiveness of therapy); “O-type” – organizational and economic aspects (interaction with staff (rudeness, unwillingness to explain the meaning of manipulations, imposition of services, etc.), waiting time for an appointment, reception or test results, cleanliness and comfort, geolocation of the clinic, value for money); “C-type” – mixed complaints (a combination of medical and organizational components).

There is a ready-made variable in the database – the addressee of the complaint – a doctor or a clinic. However, our study (Kalabikhina et al. 2024) showed that this is a rougher classification of the complaint type, which does not allow for a prompt response to monitoring the quality of medical services, if it is established, due to various management tasks. The division of complaints about a doctor and a clinic cannot be a prototype of the division of complaints about the effectiveness of treatment and organizational deficiencies. A significant part of reviews about doctors contains O-type complaints, and about clinics – M-type complaints (for example, among complaints about doctors, there are 34.7% of M-type complaints, 38% of O-type and 27.2% of C-type). Our proposal is to train artificial intelligence to recognize the nature of complaints specifically in terms of M-type and O-type.

For Moscow reviews, the classification was carried out using manual tagging methods – based on the majority of votes for the type of review. Each review was annotated by 3 annotators¹. If at least one annotator indicated that the class could not be determined unambiguously, the review was classified as #N/A – impossible to determine unambiguously. The “majority” principle was used to determine the complaint type. A high level of inter-expert agreement was achieved during manual labeling: the opinions of at least two out of three annotators coincided in 91.5% of cases. Only reviews with an unambiguous classification were included in the analysis (#N/A were excluded). For reviews from other cities, classification by type was carried out into three classes using supervised machine learning methods based on logistic regression (M – complaints about treatment and diagnostics, O – complaints about the organization, C – complaints mixed by type). The classification accuracy was 88%.

3. Large group of medical specialties. The specific medical specialties were divided into large groups. For example, all surgeons (plastic, vascular and other surgeons) were defined in the group “surgeon”. The correspondence of medical specialties to large groups is presented in Appendix (Table A1).

Sample structure and description of variables

- **CITY** – the name of a city (Volgograd, Voronezh, Yekaterinburg, Kazan, Krasnodar, Krasnoyarsk, Moscow, Nizhny Novgorod, Novosibirsk, Omsk, Perm, Rostov-on-Don, Samara, St. Petersburg, Ufa, Chelyabinsk). All the cities considered are with a population of more than one million people.
- **TEXT** – the text of the review, including a detailed description of patient dissatisfaction with the quality and/or organization of medical services.
- **GENDER** – gender of the review author (2 – female, 1 – male, 0 – cannot be determined). Created variable.
- **CLASS** – group of reasons for dissatisfaction with medical care (0 – issues of medical content (M-type), 1 – issues of organizational support (O-type), 2 – mixed (combined) class (C-type), #N/A – cannot be clearly determined). Created variable.
- **DAY** – day of the month the review was posted.
- **MONTH** – month the review was posted.
- **YEAR** – year the review was posted.
- **DOCTOR_OR_CLINIC** – what or who is the review dedicated to – the doctor or the clinic.
- **SPEC** – physician specialty (for observations where the review is dedicated to the physician).
- **GROUP_SPEC** – a large group of a physician’s specialty (see Appendix, Table A1). Created variable.
- **ID** – observation identifier.

¹ Annotators are experts who manually classified the reviews. In this study, these were three trained experts who independently rated each review according to the criteria: medical (M), organizational (O), or mixed (combined) (C) problems.

Distribution of the number of negative reviews by cities with a population of over one million (on the infodocor.ru platform for the period 2012-2023)

An analysis of the geographical distribution of 18,492 negative reviews showed a significant concentration of complaints in two capital cities. Moscow and St. Petersburg together account for 56.6% of all requests (8,108 and 2,356 reviews, respectively). Among other cities, Nizhny Novgorod stands out (1,441 reviews, 7.8%), while other million-plus cities show a comparatively smaller volume of complaints – from 1.2% (Perm) to 4.0% (Kazan).

It should be understood that such a distribution of negative reviews reflects, in addition to the differentiation of the quality of medical services, different population sizes, potentially higher activity of residents of the capitals in using online platforms to assess the quality of services and/or the volume of medical services in these regions per capita. Despite this, the value of the additional information collected and produced exists. For each of the 16 cities, we received at least 1,000 negative reviews, which allows us to conduct a comparative analysis of patient experience in the largest cities of Russia.

Database application

The data are suitable for analyzing patient dissatisfaction trends with medical services in Russia over the period from July 2012 to August 2023 in all Russian cities with a population of more than 1 million people. This dataset could be particularly useful for healthcare providers, policymakers, and researchers interested in understanding patient experiences and identifying areas for quality improvement in Russian healthcare. Some potential applications include:

- Analyzing geographic patterns of patient complaints based on a comparison of data between Russian cities with a population of over one million;
- Studying patient dissatisfaction dynamics over the course of the presented period;
- Identifying common reasons for dissatisfaction with medical care (based on content analysis of complaint texts);
- Comparing levels of dissatisfaction of patients who received medical services from specialists of different groups medical of specialties;
- Assessing gender differences in patient complaints.

The database provides rich qualitative data in the form of full-text reviews, allowing for in-depth analysis of patient experiences. The structured variables like city, date, doctor/clinic information, etc. enable quantitative analysis as well. This combination of qualitative and quantitative data makes it possible to gain a comprehensive understanding of patient dissatisfaction patterns in Russia's healthcare system over more than a decade.

For researchers specifically interested in healthcare quality issues, this dataset could serve as an important resource for studying patient experiences and outcomes in Russia's medical system. The longitudinal nature of the data (2012–2023) allows us not only to track the overall dynamics of patient satisfaction, but also to identify differences in this dynamics between cities, as well as to compare regional indicators over different time periods.

The database thus provides a valuable array of information on specific problems in the provision of health care based on patient complaints. The data can be used to inform pol-

icy decisions, develop quality-of-care programs, and further research aimed at improving healthcare in Russia.

Applications of dataset for inequality research:

1. **Geographic inequality** – identifying differences in patient dissatisfaction between cities.
2. **Gender disparities** – an assessment of the quality of medical care provided to men and women under conditions of equal access to healthcare guaranteed by the state.

An example of examining gender differences in patient reviews

According to our classification, women make up 68% of all authors of negative reviews in this database, men – 23%, in 9% of cases the gender could not be determined. In addition to the content analysis of reviews by gender, a number of questions can be considered: (1) in which cities does the ratio of patient reviews by gender deviate from the average, (2) what types of reviews predominate among women and men, (3) in which specialties do reviews of men and women predominate, etc.

For example, the most striking disproportions are observed in specialist areas: in dermatology and urology, women more often complain about medical aspects (M-type complaints), and men – about organizational ones (O-type complaints), while in functional diagnostics this structure is the opposite. In neurology and dentistry, patients of both sexes predominantly leave M-type reviews.

An example of examining the relationship between the structure of patient complaints and regional health care resources

In order to identify the relationship between the resource provision of the healthcare system and the nature of patient experience, we compared the ratio of types of patient reviews (M, O, C) and indicators of medical infrastructure in Russian cities from official statistics. For this purpose, a correlation analysis was conducted between official data from the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat)² for the period 2017–2023³, characterizing the medical infrastructure in Russian cities with a population of over a million (year-by-year values of the number of beds, doctors, mid-level medical personnel per 10 thousand people and the capacity of polyclinics⁴), and the structure of patient feedback by complaint classes (M-type per 10 thousand people, O-type per 10 thousand people, as well as the O-type to M-type complaints ratio⁵). The conducted correlation analysis did not confirm the hypothesis about

2 Indicators of medical infrastructure are taken from the Rosstat releases “Regions of Russia. Main socio-economic indicators of cities” (URL: <https://rosstat.gov.ru/folder/210/document/13206>) (date of request: 10.08.25) for the period 2017–2023.

3 The analysis is based on the full set of reviews from 2012–2023, however, in our example the indicators of medical infrastructure are averaged over 2017–2023 – a period containing 90.4% of all observations (16.713 out of 18.492) and ensuring representativeness of the comparisons.

4 Capacity of polyclinics per 10 thousand people – capacity of outpatient institutions (visits per shift per 10 thousand residents).

5 The O/M ratio is calculated as the ratio of the number of complaints of an organizational nature (O) to medical ones (M). O/M values >1 indicate the prevalence of organizational problems, values <1 indicate the prevalence of medical aspects in complaints. The choice of O-type reviews in the numerator and M-type reviews in the denominator is due to the fact that the O/M values for all cities were >1, which facilitates the interpretation of the results.

the presence of a stable relationship between the indicators of resource availability (provision of beds, doctors, nursing staff and capacity of polyclinics per 10 thousand people) and the number of complaints about medical and organizational aspects, also calculated per 10 thousand population of the cities from the studied sample. The correlation coefficients throughout the period 2017–2023 were statistically insignificant in most cases. The data obtained suggest that the reasons for patient dissatisfaction lie not (only) in the plane of resource availability, but in the area of their effective use, organization of work of medical institutions and other quality parameters of the healthcare system.

An interesting result is the discovery of a strong positive relationship between the number of medical and organizational complaints within each city ($r \in [0.55; 0.96]$). This indicates that in cities with high dissatisfaction with medical care, the problems are systemic in nature, affecting both clinical and organizational components.

Database limitations

As shown in our previous studies (Kalabikhina et al. 2024; Kalabikhina et al. 2025), the analysis of patient reviews has several fundamental limitations that are important to consider when interpreting the results:

1. Focus on negative reviews

The database includes only the most negative reviews (one star out of five), which, on the one hand, allows identifying the most acute problems (for example, “refusal of hospitalization”, “three-month waiting list”), but on the other hand, it does not allow analyzing the range of moderately negative reviews (two to four stars). In our works (Kalabikhina et al. 2024; Kalabikhina et al. 2025), we demonstrate that expanding the sample to mixed reviews requires special classification methods, which is planned in future studies.

2. Subjectivity of data

The reviews reflect personal experience and may be subject to cognitive biases. However, our methods (Kalabikhina et al. 2024), including the analysis of large arrays (18,492 reviews) and clear classification criteria (medical/organizational problems), allow us to identify stable systemic patterns.

3. Lack of context

The lack of data on the type of institution and the socio-economic status of patients limits the depth of the analysis. However, as we noted in (Kalabikhina et al. 2025), even such limited data remains valuable for identifying structural problems, and their addition to contextual variables is a promising area for further research.

Ethical Considerations

This study analyzed anonymized, publicly available patient reviews. The presented database has been stripped of all personal information that could help identify a person. No ethical approval was required as per institutional guidelines for secondary data analysis. Gender classification was based on linguistic patterns and may not capture non-binary identities.

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Appendix

Table A1. Grouping of medical specialties (in English)*

Medical specialties	Enlargement
Abdominal surgeon	Surgeon
Obstetrician	Gynecologist
Allergist	Allergist
Andrologist	Urologist
Anesthetist	Surgeon
Venereologist	Dermatologist
Vertebrologist	Neurologist
Laboratory diagnostics doctor	Clinical and diagnostic laboratory
MRI doctor (Magnetic resonance imaging)	Functional Diagnostics
GP (general practitioner)	Therapist
Sports medicine doctor	Therapist
Functional diagnostics doctor	Functional Diagnostics
Geneticist	Clinical and diagnostic laboratory
Gastroenterologist	Gastroenterologist
Hematologist	Hematologist
Hepatologist	Gastroenterologist
Gynecologist	Gynecologist
Gynecologist-endocrinologist	Gynecologist
Hirudotherapist	Alternative science
Dermatologist	Dermatologist
Defectologist	Speech therapist
Diabetologist	Endocrinologist
Nutritionist	Endocrinologist
Immunologist	Allergist
Implantologist	Surgeon
Physical therapy instructor	Rehabilitation specialist
Infectious disease specialist	Infection
Cardiologist	Cardiologist
Cardiac surgeon	Cardiac surgeon
Kinesiologist	Alternative science
Coloproctologist	Proctologist
Cosmetologist	Dermatologist
Laser therapist	Dermatologist
Speech therapist	Speech therapist

Medical specialties	Enlargement
Mammologist	Oncologist**
Manual therapist	Manual therapist
Masseur	Physiotherapist
Mycologist	Dermatologist
Expert in narcology	Psychiatrist
Neurologist	Neurologist
Neuropsychologist	Psychiatrist
Neurosurgeon	Surgeon
Neonatologist	Therapist
Nephrologist	Urologist
Oncologist	Oncologist
Orthodontist	Dentist
Orthopedist	Orthopedist
Osteopath	Alternative science
Otolaryngologist	Otorhinolaryngologist
Ophthalmologist	Ophthalmologist
Ophthalmic surgeon	Ophthalmologist
Periodontist	Dentist
Pediatrician	Therapist
Plastic surgeon	Surgeon
Podiatrist	Dermatologist
Occupational pathologist	Therapist
Psychiatrist	Psychiatrist
Psychotherapist	Psychiatrist
Pulmonologist	Pulmonologist
Rheumatologist	Allergist
Radiologist	Functional Diagnostics
Reproductive specialist	Reproductive specialist
Reflexologist	Alternative science
Sexologist	Psychiatrist
Somnologist	Psychiatrist
Vascular surgeon	Angiosurgeon
Computer tomography specialist	Functional Diagnostics
Dentist	Dentist
Dental hygienist	Dentist
Orthopedic dentist	Dentist
Dentist-therapist	Dentist

Medical specialties	Enlargement
Dental surgeon	Dentist
Audiologist	Speech therapist
Therapist	Therapist
Thoracic surgeon	Surgeon
Traumatologist	Traumatologist
Transfusiologist	Hematologist
Trichologist	Dermatologist
Ultrasound diagnostician	Functional Diagnostics
Urologist	Urologist
Physiotherapist	Physiotherapist
Phlebologist	Phlebologist
Phthisiologist	Phthisiologist
Surgeon	Surgeon
Maxillofacial surgeon	Surgeon
Endocrinologist	Endocrinologist
Endoscopist	Functional Diagnostics
Epileptologist	Neurologist

Note: * We thank Anton Nikolaev for his help; ** Included in the oncology group due to its frequent overlap with oncological diagnoses, particularly breast cancer.